

NAVIGATING ECONOMIC PEAKS: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF EMPLOYMENT TRENDS IN THE POPULATION OF ACTIVE ENTERPRISES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper explores the intricate landscape of employment within the population of active enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. Through an extensive analysis of statistical data, the study aims to provide insights into the dynamic relationship between enterprises and employment, examining trends, challenges, and the broader economic impact on the mountainous region.

1. Introduction:

Employment is a vital component of regional development, and this paper focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area to unravel the employment dynamics within the population of active enterprises. The study aims to

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analyze employment trends, sectoral contributions, and the overall impact on the local economy during the specified decade.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a rigorous quantitative approach, this research compiles and analyzes data from official reports, enterprise surveys, and relevant publications. Key indicators such as employment growth rates, sectoral distribution of jobs, and the influence of economic fluctuations are examined to provide a comprehensive understanding of the employment landscape in the Romanian Mountain Area.

3. Employment Growth Patterns:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to employment growth within the population of active enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as overall employment figures, sectoral variations, and the impact of economic events are scrutinized to assess the region's resilience in the face of changing employment dynamics.

4. Sectoral Analysis:

The paper delves into a sectoral analysis, examining the distribution of employment across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Area. Insights into key sectors driving employment, their contributions to the regional economy, and variations in sectoral employment trends are discussed.

5. Challenges and Opportunities:

Analyzing the challenges and opportunities encountered by enterprises and the workforce in the Romanian Mountain Area, this section investigates factors such as workforce skill gaps, sector-specific challenges, and opportunities for employment diversification. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for shaping policies that support sustainable job creation.

6. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of employment trends, the paper investigates the contributions of active enterprises to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), household income, and overall economic

stability. The interconnectedness between employment, enterprise activities, and regional development is explored.

7. Trends and Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing employment dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Area. Considerations such as technological advancements, demographic shifts, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective.

7. Results:

For enterprises with growth rate measured in employment (10% growth or more) – number, the related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 226349.91, 13997.826, 246416.00, 46425.535, 2155330317.691, -.924, .661, -.789, 1.279, 130479, 144988, 275467, 259915.00.

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_2: ARIMA(0,1,0); S2 - Model_3: Holt; S3 - Model_4: Holt; S4 - Model_5: Simple; S5 - Model_6: Holt; S6 - Model_7: ARIMA(0,1,0); S7 - Model_8: ARIMA(0,1,0); S8 - Model_9: Holt; S9 - Model_10: Simple; S10 - Model_11: ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_12: ARIMA(0,1,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .272, .410, -.091, .864, -.091, -.085; R-square .703, .287, -2.220E-16, 1.000, -2.220E-16, .083; RMSE 4519.692, 7040.894, .000, 25520.564, .000, 243.723; MAPS 12,161, 15,624, .000, 59,649, .000, 1,409; MaxAPE 40.866, 42.025, .000, 163.445, .000, 4.375; MAE 2774.496, 4129.489, .000, 15149.440, .000, 184.316; MaxAE 11279,208, 18900,530, .000, 67583,600, .000, 412,260; Normalized BIC 16,054, 2,107, 13,630, 20,525, 13,630, 13,709.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I5 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_2: 1.110E-16, .668, 25520.564, 7.518; S2-Model_3: .788, .785, 1790.226, 5.160; S3-Model_4: .864, .786, 1461.710, 4.697; S4-Model_5: -.091, .656, 7446.962, 6.048; S5-Model_6: .772, .924, 1530.955, 7.041; S6-Model_7: .000, .883, 812,411, 5,460; S7-

Model_8: 2.220E-16, .802, 1067.647, 10.379; S8-Model_9: .719, .801, 891.685, 11.442; S9-Model_10: -.062, .277, 6941.910, 10.096; S10-Model_11 -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 4455.942, 59.649; S11-Model_12 4.441E-16, .853, 2316.294, 18.444.

Table 22. Prediction analysis for I5

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
SECT/TIME- Model_1	Forecast	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
	UCL	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
	LCL	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1-Model_2	Forecast	286331	297196	308060	318925	329789	340653	351518	362382
	UCL	344063	378841	408054	434388	458881	482066	504261	525672
	LCL	228600	215551	208066	203462	200697	199241	198775	199093
S2-Model_3	Forecast	32136	33132	34128	35124	36120	37115	38111	39107
	UCL	36186	37203	38220	39236	40253	41269	42285	43302
	LCL	28086	29061	30036	31011	31987	32962	33937	34913
S3-Model_4	Forecast	27123	27927	28732	29537	30341	31146	31950	32755
	UCL	30429	31235	32041	32850	33660	34472	35287	36105
	LCL	23816	24620	25423	26224	27023	27820	28614	29405
S4-Model_5	Forecast	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569
	UCL	103162	110035	115308	119754	123671	127212	130469	133500
	LCL	69976	63103	57830	53384	49467	45926	42669	39638
S5-Model_6	Forecast	27949	29484	31019	32553	34088	35623	37158	38693
	UCL	31412	33011	34608	36205	37800	39395	40988	42581

	LCL	24486	25957	27429	28902	30377	31852	33328	34805
S6-Model_7	Forecast	15747	16421	17094	17768	18442	19116	19790	20463
	UCL	17585	19020	20278	21444	22551	23617	24652	25661
	LCL	13909	13822	13911	14093	14333	14614	14927	15265
S7-Model_8	Forecast	12023	12659	13296	13932	14569	15206	15842	16479
	UCL	14438	16075	17479	18763	19970	21122	22232	23310
	LCL	9607	9244	9113	9102	9168	9290	9452	9648
S8-Model_9	Forecast	9930	10448	10966	11485	12003	12521	13039	13558
	UCL	11947	12475	13003	13531	14059	14588	15115	15643
	LCL	7913	8421	8929	9438	9946	10455	10963	11472
S9-Model_10	Forecast	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193
	UCL	52661	58622	63253	67177	70644	73784	76675	79368
	LCL	21726	15765	11134	7210	3743	603	-2288	-4982
S10- Model_11	Forecast	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262
	UCL	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190
	LCL	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667
S11- Model_12	Forecast	23614	25309	27005	28700	30396	32091	33787	35482
	UCL	28853	32719	36080	39180	42112	44926	47650	50302
	LCL	18374	17899	17929	18220	18679	19256	19923	20662

For persons employed in the population of active enterprises in t – number, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 1237614.27, 25923.295, 1235524.00, 85977.843, 7392189565.418, -.676, .661, .178, 1.279, 277991, 1065478, 1343469.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 Holt; S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 Simple; S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,1,0); S6 - Model_6 Holt; S7 - Model_7 Holt; S8 - Model_8 Holt; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,1,0); S10 - Model_10 Holt; S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,1,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .318, .399, -.147, .836, -.147, -.118; R-square .533, .383, -6.661E-15, 1.000, -6.661E-15, -2.864E-15; RMSE 13145.718, 18822.416, .000, 67622.356, .000, 466.571; MAPS 6,804, 5,460, .000, 18,138, .000, 1,010; MaxAPE 27,439, 38,674, .000, 145,785, .000, 2,381; MAE 8771.078, 12024.577, .000, 42279.849, .000, 306.706; MaxAE

28705,950, 40884,616, .000, 144862,350, .000, 969,842; Normalized BIC 18,233, 2,242, 15,135, 22,679, 15,135, 15,302.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I6 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: .721, .443, 67622,356, 3,463; S2-Model_2: -6.661E-15, -6.661E-15, 25823.955, 3.862; S3-Model_3: -.147, .222, 12610.071, 6.357; S4-Model_4: 5.995E-15, 5.995E-15, 19420.163, 5.258; S5-Model_5: .000, .929, 4236,871, 4,240; S6-Model_6: .768, .912, 2362,232, 3,367; S7-Model_7: .693, .965, 1555,237, 4,501; S8-Model_8: .836, .312, 5369.472, 18.138; S9-Model_9: .000, .441, 9623.292, 6.705; S10-Model_10: .628, .296, 6294,236, 16,952; S11-Model_11: .000, .880, 2830,738, 8,806.

Table 23. Prediction analysis for I6

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	1329934	1347723	1365512	1383301	1401090	1418879	1436668
	UCL	1482906	1500717	1518555	1536431	1554356	1572340	1590395
	LCL	1176961	1194729	1212469	1230171	1247824	1265418	1282942
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	481753	481753	481753	481753	481753	481753	481753
	UCL	539292	539292	539292	539292	539292	539292	539292
	LCL	424213	424213	424213	424213	424213	424213	424213
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	121991	121991	121991	121991	121991	121991	121991
	UCL	150088	161725	170655	178183	184815	190812	196326

	LCL	93894	82257	73327	65799	59167	53171	47656
S4-	Forecast	284200	284200	284200	284200	284200	284200	284200
Model_4:	UCL	327470	327470	327470	327470	327470	327470	327470
	LCL	240929	240929	240929	240929	240929	240929	240929
S5-	Forecast	108925	112934	116944	120953	124962	128971	132980
Model_5:	UCL	118510	126489	133544	140122	146394	152448	158339
	LCL	99341	99380	100343	101784	103530	105494	107622
S6-	Forecast	66379	68566	70753	72941	75128	77315	79502
Model_6:	UCL	71723	73960	76198	78434	80671	82907	85142
	LCL	61035	63172	65309	67447	69585	71724	73863
S7-	Forecast	43332	45659	47987	50315	52642	54970	57297
Model_7:	UCL	46850	49236	51621	54005	56388	58770	61152
	LCL	39814	42083	44353	46625	48897	51169	53443
S8-	Forecast	33762	34824	35885	36947	38008	39069	40131
Model_8:	UCL	45909	46970	48032	49093	50155	51216	52277
	LCL	21616	22677	23739	24800	25861	26923	27984
S9-	Forecast	114374	117067	119759	122451	125144	127836	130528
Model_9:	UCL	136144	147853	157465	165990	173821	181160	188125
	LCL	92605	86280	82053	78912	76466	74512	72932
S10-	Forecast	27319	28546	29773	31000	32227	33454	34681
Model_10:	UCL	41558	42785	44012	45239	46466	47693	48920
	LCL	13081	14308	15535	16762	17989	19216	20443
S11-	Forecast	39637	41675	43713	45751	47789	49828	51866
Model_11:	UCL	46041	50731	54805	58559	62108	65513	68808
	LCL	33234	32619	32622	32944	33471	34142	34923

Figure 3.14. Graphical forecasting analysis for I6

Regarding employees in the population of active enterprises in t – number, the related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, the distance, minimum, maximum, 5, 50, 75, thus 1123610.91, 17809.719, 1096497.00, 59068.157, 3489047181818181, .872, .661, .844, 1.279, 214040, 1035313, 1249353, 1091701.00.

The models used for forecast analysis are S1 - Model_1 Brown; S2 - Model_2 Brown; S3 - Model_3 Brown; S4 - Model_4 Brown; S5 - Model_5 Brown; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,1,0); S7 - Model_7 Brown; S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 Holt; S10 - Model_10 Holt; S11 - Model_11 Brown.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .067, .304, -.159, .705, -.159, -.152; R-square .571, .386, 1.110E-15, 1.000, 1.110E-15, .001; RMSE 10103.357, 15438.272, .000, 53066.242, .000, 172.219; MAP 5,593, 6,505, .000, 20,976, .000, .638; MaxAPE 25,259, 45,791, .000, 168,119, .000, 1,679; MAE 6567.129, 10153.786, .000, 35236.459, .000, 108.303; MaxAE 22989.688, 34039.361, .000, 114368.959, .000, 384.300; Normalized BIC 17,194, 2,776, 12,923, 21,977, 12,923, 13,077.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I7 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -.120, .193, 53066,242, 3,219; S2-Model_2: -.106, .004, 25867.101, 3.564; S3-Model_3: .007, .533, 11589.404, 5.579; S4-Model_4: -.124, .326, 12877.150, 3.470; S5-Model_5: .035, .952, 2785.086, 2.746; S6-Model_6: 1.110E-16, .842, 1909.455, 3.395; S7-Model_7: -.159, .977, 841.774, 2.389; S8-Model_8: 1.110E-15, 1.110E-15, 5211.335, 20.976; S9-Model_9: .705, .769, 2728,883, 2,328; S10-Model_10: .628, .327, 3789.787, 17.318; S11-Model_11: -.127, .924, 574,064, 2,128.

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	1194648	1206796	1218944	1231092	1243239	1255387	1267535
	UCL	1312887	1471176	1661329	1878671	2120061	2383230	2666448
	LCL	1076409	942416	776559	583512	366418	127544	-131378
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	473801	470270	466738	463206	459675	456143	452611
	UCL	531437	599144	682383	778877	887094	1E+6	1E+6
	LCL	416166	341396	251093	147535	32256	-93641	-229311
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	112164	113574	114984	116395	117805	119216	120626
	UCL	137986	167569	202750	242794	287172	335493	387453
	LCL	86341	59579	27219	-10004	-51561	-97061	-146201
S4-Model_4:	Forecast	248532	249708	250884	252060	253237	254413	255589
	UCL	277224	313865	358239	409212	466020	528114	595074
	LCL	219840	185551	143529	94909	40453	-19289	-83896

S5- Model_5:	Forecast	98022	101623	105224	108825	112426	116027	119627
	UCL	104228	114065	125074	137112	150069	163865	178436
	LCL	91817	89182	85374	80538	74783	68188	60818
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	57890	59170	60450	61730	63009	64289	65569
	UCL	62209	65278	67931	70369	72668	74870	76998
	LCL	53570	53061	52968	53091	53351	53709	54141
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	36401	38763	41125	43487	45849	48211	50573
	UCL	38277	42957	48143	53760	59759	66103	72765
	LCL	34525	34569	34107	33214	31939	30319	28381
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	23538	23538	23538	23538	23538	23538	23538
	UCL	35150	35150	35150	35150	35150	35150	35150
	LCL	11927	11927	11927	11927	11927	11927	11927
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	92905	94359	95813	97267	98721	100175	101629
	UCL	99078	100564	102049	103534	105020	106505	107990
	LCL	86732	88154	89576	90999	92422	93844	95267
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	21742	22506	23270	24034	24798	25562	26326
	UCL	30315	31079	31843	32607	33371	34135	34899
	LCL	13169	13933	14697	15461	16225	16989	17753
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	21450	22107	22764	23421	24078	24735	25392
	UCL	22729	24967	27550	30427	33564	36937	40526
	LCL	20171	19247	17978	16415	14592	12533	10258

Table 24. Prediction analysis for I7

Figure 3.15. Graphical forecasting analysis for I7

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of employment trends within the population of active enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's employment dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable employment growth in the mountainous region.

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